

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B324
Date: 03 September 2007
Take Off: 10:41:15
Landing: 15:42:05
Flight Time: 5h00m50

Campaign: CIRRUS

Operating Area: Chilbolton and SW approaches

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Luc Lathouwers	Directflight
3	CCM 1	Jo Green	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Claire Lee	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Jamie Trembath	FAAM
6	AVAPS / Core Chem / CCM2	Doug Anderson	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	FAAM
8	Shims SWS	Martin Glew	Met Office
9	AIRES	Stuart Rogers	Met Office
10	MARSS / Deimos	Rob King	Met Office
11	Mission Scientist 2	Paul Barratt	Met Office
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FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B324
 Date: 03 September
 Project: CAESAR
 Location: Chilbolton & SW

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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100344		ASP	0.17 kft	128	open
100645		QNH	0.17 kft	128	QNH 1019
102408		Start-Up	0.17 kft	128	
102943		Taxi	0.16 kft	128	
104115		T/O	0.47 kft	028	
104948		Video	9.3 kft	201	DFC to RFC
105255		jw/nev zeroed	10.0 kft	262	
105915		WAS	10.2 kft	199	bottles 29 and 30 filled
111144	111537	Profile 1	20.4 - 24.0 kft	067	
111537	111920	Run 1	24.0 kft	060	
111831		waters zeroed	24.0 kft	056	
112556	112804	Run 2	24.0 kft	273	
112805	113440	Profile 2	24.0 - 27.6 kft	267	
112950		500 ft/min	25.3 kft	266	
113740	114442	Profile 2	27.5 - 31.0 kft	097	
114442	114455	Run 3	31.0 kft	060	
114548		JW zeroed	31.0 kft	046	
115220	120938	Run 4	31.0 kft	271	
115902		Video	31.0 kft	269	Tapes changed
121120	121626	Run 5	31.0 kft	358	down sun run
121858	122152	Run 6	31.0 kft	186	into sun run
122331	122812	Run 7	31.1 kft	056	
122812	123505	Profile 3	31.1 - 34.0 kft	052	
123506	124259	Run 8	34.0 kft	056	
125039	125247	Run 9	34.1 - 34.0 kft	281	
125247	125506	Profile 4	34.0 - 32.0 kft	271	
125506	130126	Profile 5	32.0 - 35.0 kft	266	
130126	130547	Run 10	35.0 kft	270	
130548	130702	Profile 6	35.0 - 34.0 kft	268	
131403	133006	Run 11	34.0 kft	057	
132739		Video	34.0 kft	058	Tapes changed
133742	134205	Run 12	34.1 - 34.0 kft	284	
134205	134423	Profile 7	34.0 - 35.0 kft	269	
134424	140355	Run 13	35.0 kft	269	
134436		sonde 1	35.1 kft	269	
140635	141858	Run 14	35.0 kft	074	
141859	142140	Profile 8	35.0 - 33.0 kft	060	
142237	142514	Orbit 1	33.1 - 33.0 kft	037	left hand 40 degrees
142654	142915	Orbit 2	33.0 - 32.9 kft	290	left hand 40 degrees
143239	144551	Run 15	33.1 - 33.0 kft	345	
144613	145028	Profile 9	33.0 - 35.1 kft	002	
145227	151456	Run 16	35.0 kft	059	
145640		Video	35.0 kft	059	Tapes changed
154205		Land	0.14 kft	032	
154721		Shutdown	0.13 kft	306	52'04.36 N 0'37.50W
154748		ASP	0.13 kft	306	closed

GEOSTROPHIC WIND SCALE
IN KNOTS FOR ISOBARS AT 4 MS INTERVALS
POLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION

B324 Track 03-SEP-07

FAAM Sortie Brief

CAESAR flight - Radar validation and intercomparison of cirrus microphysics

Flight no: B324

Date: 3rd September 2007

Take Off: 1015Z (11:15 local).

Aim:

The aim of this sortie is to obtain a good statistical representation of the in-situ microphysics of a frontal cirrus case, which is coincident with radar measurements from Chilbolton. A few runs above and below the cloud are to be made for radiative measurements, in addition to the saw tooth manoeuvres for the in-situ measurements.

Weather conditions:

Convective, frontal or Lee wave cirrus, ideally with clear skies below. It is essential to be able to get just above the cirrus. Small amounts of low cloud are acceptable if they are measurable by the radar.

Location:

On Chilbolton radial.

Chilbolton is at: N51:08:42 W01:26:18

Clearances:

NOTAMS will be required for dropping sondes.

Communications

With operators at Chilbolton (if relevant) via SATCOM or VHF radio (130.575 MHz, call-sign "Radsearch").

Instruments required:

Critical: SID2, 2DC, 2DP, FFSSP, Temp, Humidity (incl FWVS)

Desirable: SID1, CIPs, AVAPS, ARIES, SWS, MARSS, TAFTS, SHIMS, Heimann, Core chem (automatic mode acceptable)

Flight no: B324

Date: 3rd September 2007

	Time Z	Manoeuvre	Duration (min)	Total time (min)
1	1015Z	Takeoff from Cranfield & Transit to Chilbolton area	35	35
2	1050Z	1 straight and level run along Chilbolton radial, 1000ft below cirrus base, of 10 mins	10	45
3	1100Z	Perform a series of ascending and descending profiles in a saw tooth pattern through the cirrus to an altitude of 1000ft above and below the cloud respectively, along radial to go over Chilbolton.	130	175
4	1310Z	2 SLR above lower cirrus layer into and out of Sun, of 5 mins. (SWS to do angles above and below)	15	190
5	1325Z	Profile ascent to FL350	15	205
6	1340Z	1 straight and level run at max alt, of 10 mins. Drop 2 or 3 sondes. Satellite overpass (1345Z) ideally during run.	10	215
7	1350Z	Reciprocal straight and level run above cloud, of 10 mins.	10	225
8	1400Z	Profile descent to 1000ft below cirrus	20	245
9	1420Z	Perform 2 orbits below cirrus at 55deg or max bank angle	10	255
10	1430Z	transit towards clear sky	30	285
11	1500Z	Perform a box pattern including 2 minute legs towards, across and away from Sun at FL240 in clear sky	15	300
12	1515Z	Transit to Cranfield	15	315
13	1530Z	Land		

Instrument operational instructions:

Nev

- when out of cloud in a straight and level run zero it

ARIES and SWS

- Both instruments must point in the same direction (either zenith or nadir) as each other, except during cal. ARIES needs to tell SWS where it is pointing.
- Majority of time should be towards the cloud (or sea at 100ft), however, still need some data pointing away to characterise the atmosphere above and below the cloud (e.g. ~2 of 10 min run)
- For orbits both instruments should view towards cloud for whole time
- When close to the area of operation (~15mins) take data during both transits

ARIES

- If it is still unstable for zenith views (shutter open) at high altitudes, it is better to get 1 min of good data in a 10 min run (with rest of time with shutter closed viewing calcs or nadir) than all bad data – let SWS know which viewing direction and when.

SWS

- Continue to take data during the profiles
- Ensure that the signal does not saturate. Request extra orbits if necessary.

Satellite Overpass:

Mission Scientist De-Brief

B324 - CAESAR over Chilbolton area

03/09/07

Mission Scientist: Clare Lee

Aim:

The aim of the sortie was to obtain in-situ statistics of cirrus over and around Chilbolton. Due to the layer of cirrus being too high, only the lower levels of the cirrus were measured with the cloud physics probes. The majority of the flight was therefore directed to obtaining good remote sensing observations and relying on the Chilbolton lidar and radars to provide cloud properties.

This flight was coincident with an AIRS overpass towards the edge of the swath. CloudSat's orbit was too far to the West. All Chilbolton instruments were operating well and the 94GHz radar was mounted on the steerable dish to provide radial information.

At the end of the sortie clear sky conditions were sought to perform an SWS and SHIMS in-flight calibration, however there was always some high level thin wispy cirrus or contrails which would have compromised the data and hence this was not performed.

Weather:

The conditions had been forecasted to produce 2 layers of cirrus one at ~20kft and the other at ~40kft. In reality bases started at 10km (33kft) to 11.5 km, as identified by Chilbolton. For the whole duration there was ~4/8 low level Cu (<8000ft). At other levels it was completely clear and no haze. The cirrus base did fluctuate with location and time as it flowed over the operating area from the NNW.

Contrails:

No contrails were made with the 146 during the whole sortie. Other aircraft were seen to be making contrails above 35kft, but were only persistent at much higher altitudes.

Sortie:

A transit was made into the Chilbolton operating area. SWS and ARIES were both requested to make mainly zenith views during this period of relatively straight and level flying. A profile ascent was made followed by a short SLR at FL240 towards Chilbolton. The cirrus was clearly at higher altitudes. An interrupted profile to FL310 was made (still below the cirrus base) followed by a short run East to Chilbolton and a long leg West towards Dartmoor. Two reciprocal runs, into and out of the Sun, were made instead of orbits to obtain angular dependence of the cirrus above. Subsequent runs were all along the Chilbolton radial (257 deg). A profile to FL340 was made to get into the base of the cirrus. The base layer was variable, hence the aircraft had patches in and out of cloud. A profile descent (to FL320) was made as the start of the saw tooth profiles. At the bottom of the profile (when out of the cloud) extra speed was permitted to allow the aircraft up to FL350 on the next profile ascent. A run was made at FL350. Unfortunately due to the aircraft still being too heavy, we could not turn at that altitude, hence a descent was made to FL340 to turn around. A similar maneuver could not be made as issues would arise on the quick turn needed directly after Chilbolton, hence a run at FL340 was flown instead. Later on the aircraft was light enough to ascend to FL350. A sonde was released at the

beginning of the FL350 run, just before the satellite overpass, and away from populated areas. After the high level runs a profile descent to FL330 was made, to be below the cloud bases for 2 orbits of 40 degrees (max bank angle). Due to lack of time the cirrus sortie was ended to look for clear sky to calibrate SWS and SHIMS. On the run towards a suitable area a profile was made to FL350 to obtain further in-situ measurements. Heading further North the cirrus was much higher with no particles measured. During these level runs SWS and ARIES were continually measuring mainly zenith views. Unfortunately the Aberporth area was too cloudy for calibrations to be made.

Instrument Issues:

Core Chem – Started to overheat. Was switched off for a short time to cool down and was subsequently fine.

FWVS – Looked as if it was taking data. Rebooted to be sure. Unsure of the absolute numbers though. May need post processing.

SWS – reboot needed

PCASP – lost reference volts, but was fine on final descent (<4000ft)

TWC – still can't cope with high altitudes

Deimos – during testing seems to be related to noise seen on Cloud Physics measurements

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B 324 Date 3/9/07 Name CLARE LEE Page 1 of 6

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
~1044Z					Takeoff Cranfield.
					~ $\frac{1}{8}$ W, ~ $\frac{4}{8}$ Ci
1046	~	2600ft			W lower edge going through.
1050	~	6000ft			W tops. ~6000
					$\frac{6}{8}$ W lots of contrails.
					Some tops higher ~7000ft.
111144	P1	FL200	067	50°56'N 2°18'W	Profile up towards Cranfield Chilbolton
111537	P1	FL240			
111537	R1	FL240	061		Run towards Chilbolton.
					$\frac{7}{8}$ Ci ~10km base, $\frac{4}{8}$ W
111920			060		Over top of Chilbolton.
					$\frac{3}{8}$ W., Ci much higher.
111920	Blend				End run.
112556	R2	FL240	265	51°06'N 1°26'W	Run at band (to West) first ^{run.}
112816					Over Chilbolton.
112804	R2end	FL240			End run.
112804	P2↑	FL240	269		Profile along radial.
113440	P2	FL275			Interrupted due to air traffic.
113740	P2.1↑	FL275	092	50°56'N 2°18'W	Restart profile.
					Most parts in profile up but no sign of particles
114430					Note in all ^{several} profiles changes in direction to get on radial.
114442	P2end	FL310			
	R3				Over Chilbolton SUR shot
114455	R3end				run. (even though still on heading).

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B 324 Date 3/9/07 Name CLARE LEE Page 2 of 5

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
114844					Turning right.
115220	R4	FL310			Start of run + over Heading towards Dartmoor to do into + at of sun run. T = -38°C T _D = -45°C
1205					FNWS not giving sensible #'s Dag is going to check it at.
120938	R4end	FL310			
121120	R5	FL310	359		Down sun. Over Dartmoor.
121628	R5end	FL310			Finish run.
121858	R6	FL310	185		Into Sun run (further to W)
122152	R6end	FL310			
122331	R7	FL310	055		Run waiting for air traffic to let us up to higher levels.
1225					O ₂ re-heating, Dag is switching off for a short while for it to cool.
1226					Aircraft seen passing above (seen in RFE) at 33kft. - not containing.
122812	R7end	FL310			air traffic permission to climb
122812	P3↑	FL310	058	50°42'N 3°18'W	to FL340.
123505	P3end	FL340			
123505	R8	FL340			Rollout towards Chilbolton Ci base + top R Chilbolton 10km ⇒ 11.5km reported.
1237					In cloud

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B 324 Date 3/9/07 Name CLARE LEE Page 3 of 6

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					Li base seems lower to E
					(Chilbolton) + higher to W (down)
123937					Small turbulence. for ~15secs.
1240					Dendroites + larger particles.
					T _e -47.3°C, T _D -47.22°C
					Wind Sums -11°
124124					Small turbulence for ~20secs
1241					PIRES has glitch!
124221					Small turbulence for ~45secs.
124259	R8end	FC340.			End of run + over Chilbolton. Have been no contrails.
125039	R9	FC340	289		Reciprocal away from Chilbolton
125039					* over top of Chilbolton.
125247	R9end				Starting saw tooth manoeuvres.
125247	P4 ↓	FC340	272	51°08'N 1°48'W	↓
125410		32700			Out of it.
125506	P4end	FC320			Still ~ 4/8 W below.
125506	P5 ↑	FC320			
130126	P5	FC350			
130126	R10	FC350			Running on SLR as cannot turn due to too much fuel.
130510		FC350.		50°42'N 3°36'W	2D seeing Ci.
130547	R10.				End run.
130548	P6 ↓	FC350			Descending so can turn around.
		34200ft.			2D still seeing particles.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B 324 Date 3/9/07 Name CLARE LEE Page 4 of 6

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
130703	P6end	FL340	266		End profile. Turning left reciprocal. Can't get to FL350 + turn until ~ 13:40
131403	R11	FL340	059	50°42'N / 3°36'W	
1317					just came out of thin Ci T = -46.9, T _D = -47.3
132547					Not seeing the low bases we did close to Chilbolton before Chilbolton reentry little ci
132940					2D seeing particles just catching lower parts.
133010					over Chilbolton.
133006	R1end	FL340			glance part dead to E of Chilbolton. Higher part in centre of track. in it during turn.
133742	R12	FL340	276		
1338	R12				Out of cloud. (2D)
134003	P7	FL340	269		Profling up.
134424	P7end	FL350			End profile
134424	R13	FL350	269		
134436	S1	FL350			Sonde released. Ci is generally thinning
1348					Some Ci particles
1357					Sonde 1 landed.
135714					Out of ci

257 radial tracks.
RD93 Sonde.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B...324 Date 3/9/07 Name CLARE...LEE Page 5 of 6

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
140355	R13	FL350			Run ended
					Looked at images for clear area for □ SWS lat.
					then out to West area Run thickens again.
140635	R14	FL350			Run back to Chilbolton.
					In clear slot but still some thin stuff overhead (patchy)
1410					Over land. - First start of run was over sea with ~ 1/8 W.
1417.					In ci
141858	R14				End of run.
141858	P8 ↓	FL350	060		Profiling down to do orbits.
	P8 end	FL330	061.		Left hand orbit.
142157	Orbit 1	FL330			040°
142654	Orbit 2	FL330			LH 40°
					Running out of time so heading to Abernethy of clear sky cal.
143239	R15	FL330	364	50°41'N 3°18'W	Heading towards clear slot.
1440					Weather clearing in too much Ci on Martin's advice not doing cal.
144551	R15				End run
144613	P9 ↑	FL330			Getting altitude to sample
145028	P9	FL350			ci particles on way back.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B 326

Date 3/9/07

Name WARRIE LEE

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Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					Turning towards Mahan for a leg at FC350.
145227	R16	FC350	060		Start of an run before this but requested by Jamie. Ci is all very high ^(~4000ft) ~ 7/8 5/8 W below. Aircraft containing 37 V.I.F. Not persisting though. Higher contrails are persisting. Too many in distance to get clear sky.
1511					Dry at at FC350. 2/3 Ci high above. 6/8 W below nothing else.
151456	R16end	FC350			End run. Descent quickly into Cranfield. Approach into Cranfield W tops ~ 9000ft. bases ~ 5500ft.
~1545					Landing Cranfield. Instrument SWS reboot needed. PCSP lost reference volts. TWC - can't cope with high alt.

Came back at 4000ft. on last profile.
Demos noise variable effect on cloud physics.

Mission Scientist's Log

MISSION SCIENTIST 2

Flight No B 324

Date 3/09/07

Name BARRETT, P.

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Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
10.40 (Dh)		3500			less than Cu
↓		4000			~
		5500 7000			..
10.48		7400			~
					Zoff
11.14.4	P.1	20A	G6		Dewpoint - Fluro - not working - T LBS
11.16.25	A	-	-		Spike of dew point over T
11.16.50					patchy Cu below
11.28.05	P2	24.04A	266		
11.44.42	P2 Cu				Cu below on run
11.44.55	P2 Fluro				T = -41.3, Fluro (Fluro) - not working Ci - just above PL310 - thin air descending @ Higher levels
12.01.37					Dew Pt
12.18					LWC (Fluro) resampled - not set
					~
12.37.38		34.1A	S6		cloud particles - 300µm v. close dew
12.40		34.1A	-		100% Rel Humidity
12.57					T/W LWC - no signal
13.29:					dew pt > true air temp
13.33					..
13.48					very close dew / T
14.05					Satt pics - first cirrus? - or JPG artifacts?

Instruments

The 3 and 94 GHz Radars were both mounted on the steerable dish. The 35 GHz radar, Lidar ceilometer and Raman lidar were vertically pointing. All instruments appeared to be operating normally.

Conditions

Initially thick Ci thinned just before the flight, but thickened up again about a third of the way through before thinning again to the point where it could not be resolved by instruments but remained just about visible. Throughout the observation period there was broken Cu/Sc, sometimes thick enough to precipitate, although this was seen to evaporate before reaching the ground.

10:24Z	On station 34 GHz showing echoes from 9 – 11 km CAMRA from 10 – 11.5 km (Doppler)
11:05Z	Doppler signal shows Ci thinning and lowering, thin layer just below 11 km
11:34Z	METMAN on 257 Radial, performing RHIs on same.
11:41Z	METMAN inbound, dish dwelling on zenith for 5 mins
11:45Z	METMAN overhead inbound, no Ci signals in Chilbolton instruments. Thin Ci visible.
11:46Z	RHI
11:47Z	35 GHz Radar starting to see echoes again at 11.5 – 12 km
11:52Z	METMAN overhead outbound
11:53Z	35 GHz Ci level dropping, thin at ~ 11.5 km
12:00Z	METMAN off to do SWS cals
12:17Z	3 GHz Doppler giving 'pink' signal about 25-50 km down range.
12:30Z	3GHz reflectivity starting to see a signal ~11-11.5 km, out to ~ 20 km downrange
12:33Z	Dwelling on zenith
12:34Z	Ci thickening, showing up on 3, 35 and 94 GHz reflectivity. Overhead, base ~10.3 km, top ~11.5 km
12:38Z	RHIs
12:43Z	METMAN overhead inbound. Latest RHIs have such a strong Ci signal.
12:48Z	Some reflectivity signal from 3GHz at 12 km overhead, sloping down to West
13:01Z	3 GHz reflectivity and Doppler show Ci near Chilbolton at ~10.5 km
13:06Z	RHI on 330 degrees to get an idea of what's coming
13:13Z	Returning dish to 257 radial for RHI
13:21Z	Nothing on 35GHz
13:23Z	PPI
13:30Z	RHI, METMAN overhead
13:34Z	RHI to East
13:40Z	METMAN outbound
13:41Z	Dwelling on Zenith
13:45Z	RHI for overpass
13:57Z	Dwelling on Zenith

14:03Z	RHI, apparently METMAN has gone to Cornwall
14:36Z	RHIs, 35 GHz showing thin, intermittent Ci at ~12 km
14:46Z	PPI, Ci very thin if any, Looks as though METMAN is heading for home.
14:58Z	RHI
15:01Z	Successive zenith dwells, followed by home time.

Latest real-time cloud radar images

From the 35 GHz Copernicus radar at Chilbolton.
 Normal height range: [last thirty minutes](#) | [last four hours](#) | [today](#) | [yesterday](#)
 Boundary layer: [last thirty minutes](#) | [last four hours](#) | [today](#) | [yesterday](#)
[Archive](#)

Latest coherently processed Z

Latest coherently-processed vertical velocity

http://gate.chobs.rl.ac.uk/display_data/radar-copernicus_graphics/web/index.html

03/09/2007

Latest real-time 35 GHz Copernicus radar images

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Latest coherently-processed spectral width

http://gate.chobs.rl.ac.uk/display_data/radar-copernicus_graphics/web/index.html

03/09/2007

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 324

Date: 03/09/07	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 08:45:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
11:11:47	15	0.06	4	1												Start Profile 1 from FL200	
11:13:24	10	0.07	5	1												FL220	
11:14:40	20	0.07		1												FL230	
11:15:38																End of Profile 1 & Start Run1 @ FL240	
11:16:00	5	0.07	6	1													
11:18:00	2	0.02	7	1													
11:19:20																End of Run 1	
11:25:56																Start Run 2 @ FL240	
11:26:00				1	Noise												
11:28:04																End of Run 2 & Start Profile 2	
11:29:20	1	0.05														FL250	
11:31:23																FL260	
11:33:35				1												FL270	
11:38:44	1	0.04		1												FL280 Rearm 2 1	
11:40:38	5	0.16		1												FL290	
11:42:51	2	0.10		1												FL300	
11:44:42																End of Profile 2 & Start Run 3 @ FL310	
11:44:55																End of Run 3	
11:52:20																Start Run 4 @ FL310	
11:53:00	1	0.02	8	1	Noise												
11:55:00	1	0.02															
11:57:00																	
11:59:00	1	0.10															
12:01:00																	
12:03:00	3	0.15															
12:05:00					Noise												
12:07:00	1	0.09															
12:09:00																	
12:09:36																End of Run 4	
12:11:18																Start 5 @ FL310	
12:12:00																	
12:14:00					Noise												
12:16:26																End of Run 5	
12:18:58																Start Run 6 @ FL310	
12:19:00	1	0.12															
12:21:00																	
12:21:52																End of Run 6	
12:23:31																Start Run 7 @ FL310	
12:24:00			9														
12:26:00																	
12:28:11																End of Run & Start Profile 3 from FL310	
12:29:30																FL320	
12:31:44	1	0.21														FL330	

PCASP Reference Volts = 7.5	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.3	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -1.5	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = 0.13	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = N/A
PCASP Flow rate = 0.7 CC/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -1.1	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = 010	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = N/A
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = 12	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = - 3.5		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 324

Date: 03/09/07	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 08:45:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 2 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
12:34:57																End of Profile 3 & Start Run 8 @ FL340	
12:37:00	1	0.03	11	100	10	60	300								10		
12:39:00	9	0.13	13	80	10	20	500								4		
12:41:00	1	0.06	14	20	5	3	250								10		
12:43:00																End of Run 8	
12:50:38																Start Run 9 @ FL340	
12:51:00	30	0.19	22	200	10	40	300								4		
12:52:46																End of Run 9 & Start Profile 4 from FL340	
12:53:49	30	0.27	26	100	10											FL330	
12:55:06																End of Profile 4 & Start Profile 5 from FL320	
12:56:28	13	0.28														FL330	
12:59:28	2	0.03														FL340	
13:01:26																End of Profile 5 & Start Run 10 @ FL350	
13:02:00	5	0.09															
13:04:00																	
13:05:44																End of Run 5 & Start Profile 6 from FL350	
13:07:02	15	0.28	28	3	1	1	100								11	End of Profile 6 @ FL340	
13:14:04																Start Run 11 @ FL340	
13:15:00	2	0.08	20	15	5	20	200								10		
13:17:00	15	0.24	30														
13:19:00	2	0.12															
13:21:00	4	0.08															
13:23:00	3	0.38															
13:25:00	Noise																
13:27:00	1	0.04															
13:29:00	15	0.17	31	80	1												
13:30:14																End of Run 11	
13:37:42																Start Run 12 @ FL340	
13:38:00	6	0.05	40														
13:40:00	4	0.08															
13:42:05																End of Run 12 & Start Profile 7	
13:44:24																End of Profile 7 & Start Run 13 @ FL350	
13:45:00	Noise		40														
13:47:00	11	0.06		1	2	0.5											
13:49:00	12	0.12		10	1	5	200								10		
13:51:00	75	0.36	41	20	2	25	150								10		
13:53:00	Noise		42	70	4	30	125								10	PCASP Volts = 0.23	
13:55:00	Noise		43	100	2	8	100								11		
13:57:00	Noise																
13:59:00	Noise																
14:01:00	Noise																
14:03:54																End of Run 13	
14:06:30																Start Run 14 @ FL350	

PCASP Reference Volts = 7.5	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.3	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -1.5	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = 0.13	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = N/A
PCASP Flow rate = 0.7 CC/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -1.1	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = 010	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = N/A
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = 12	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = - 3.5		

FAAM Dropsonde Flight Log

Flight No.	B324	Date	03 Sep 2007	Operator	Doug Anderson	Page No.	1 of 1
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GMT	Sonde No.	Event <i>eg land, splashdown</i>	Comments <i>pressure hPa, T deg C, RH %, wind direction deg, wind speed m/s, longitude, latitude, height m</i>
13:44:39	1	Launch	237.80 -49.50 85.11 353.00 55.40 -17.40 -2.565800 50.933400 10683.80
13:56:50	1	Splashdown	998.68 15.39 53.61 352.23 4.31 -11.33 -2.492035 50.793858 -148.71

B324_SWS_SHIMS_Log.txt

```

10:07:31.40 --- - - - -
10:07:31.40 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
10:07:31.40 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
                    tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
10:07:31.40 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B324
10:07:31.40 --- - - - -
10:08:59.88 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS FAILED NIR OK
10:09:01.17 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS FAILED NIR OK
10:09:01.35 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
10:09:07.54 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR FAILED
10:09:10.65 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR FAILED
10:10:26.72 --- - - - -
10:10:26.72 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
10:10:26.72 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
                    tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
10:10:26.72 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B324
10:10:26.72 --- - - - -
10:10:38.01 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
10:10:38.19 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
10:10:38.28 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
10:10:42.29 SWS - 100 - - Sample period changed from 500ms to 100ms.
10:10:45.36 USH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 500ms to 100ms.
10:10:50.40 LSH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 500ms to 100ms.
10:11:11.00 SWS - - 35 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 35ms.
10:11:15.24 SWS - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
10:11:19.84 USH - - 300 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 300ms.
10:11:23.46 USH - - - 300 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 300ms.
10:11:28.24 LSH - - 300 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 300ms.
10:11:35.28 LSH - - - 300 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 300ms.
10:11:43.89 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
10:11:50.93 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:11:50.94 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:11:50.94 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:11:53.23 SWS - - - - Idling
10:11:55.12 LSH - - - - Idling
10:11:55.36 USH - - - - Idling
10:11:56.11 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:11:56.11 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:11:56.11 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:11:57.94 SWS - - - - Idling
10:11:59.54 USH - - - - Idling
10:11:59.74 LSH - - - - Idling
10:12:03.03 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:12:03.03 LSH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:12:03.04 USH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:12:19.35 USH - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 100ms.
10:12:23.90 USH - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 100ms.
10:12:36.83 SWS - - - - Idling
10:12:37.10 USH - - - - Idling
10:12:37.26 LSH - - - - Idling
10:12:39.11 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
10:12:43.16 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:12:43.17 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:12:43.18 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:12:44.81 USH - - - - Idling
10:12:45.00 SWS - - - - Idling
10:12:46.60 LSH - - - - Idling
10:12:47.28 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:12:47.28 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:12:47.29 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:12:48.71 SWS - - - - Idling
10:12:49.12 USH - - - - Idling
10:12:50.93 LSH - - - - Idling
10:12:51.48 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:12:51.49 LSH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:12:51.49 USH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!

```

14:19:26.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:19:28.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:28.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:28.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:32.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:19:32.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:19:32.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:19:33.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:34.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:34.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:44.87	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
14:19:47.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:19:47.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:19:47.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:21:02.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:21:04.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:21:05.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:21:07.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:21:19.67	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
14:25:16.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:25:25.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:25:26.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:25:28.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:25:29.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:25:32.40	SWS	-	-	10	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 10ms.
14:25:36.10	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
14:25:39.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:25:40.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:25:42.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:25:44.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:25:44.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:25:46.91	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
14:29:26.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:29:28.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:29:30.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:29:31.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:29:33.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:29:35.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:29:36.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:29:42.27	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 100ms.
14:29:45.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:29:45.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:29:45.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:29:51.12	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
14:29:55.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:29:55.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:29:55.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:29:57.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:29:57.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:29:57.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:30:00.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:30:00.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:30:00.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:30:02.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:30:02.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:30:02.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:30:03.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:30:03.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:30:03.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:30:04.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:30:05.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:30:05.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:30:09.33	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
14:30:12.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:30:12.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:30:12.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:35:28.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:35:43.79	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
14:35:49.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

```

10:15:50.03 --- - - - - *** For this flight a comment of the form "m
+20" means the mirror is 20 deg forward. "m
-20" means the mirror is 20 deg aft

10:43:52.25 --- - - - -
10:43:52.25 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
10:43:52.25 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
10:43:52.25 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B324
10:43:52.25 --- - - - -
10:44:06.43 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
10:44:06.53 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
10:44:06.62 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
10:44:27.72 --- - - - - *** m -90
10:44:30.15 SWS - - 30 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 30ms.
10:44:34.02 SWS - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
10:44:38.10 USH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 500ms to 100ms.
10:44:44.07 SWS - 100 - - Sample period changed from 500ms to 100ms.
10:44:54.94 USH - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
10:44:59.34 USH - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
10:45:04.42 LSH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 500ms to 100ms.
10:45:08.69 LSH - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
10:45:11.69 LSH - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
10:45:17.59 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
10:45:21.79 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:45:21.80 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:45:21.80 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:45:24.11 SWS - - - - Idling
10:45:24.15 LSH - - - - Idling
10:45:24.29 USH - - - - Idling
10:45:25.12 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:45:25.12 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:45:25.15 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:45:26.55 USH - - - - Idling
10:45:26.75 SWS - - - - Idling
10:45:26.95 LSH - - - - Idling
10:45:28.25 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:45:28.25 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:45:28.25 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:46:24.56 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:47:02.25 SWS 6F - - - - Telescope position set to 6F
10:47:05.90 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:52:36.31 --- - - - - *** stop SWS to
10:52:47.09 --- - - - - *** h what
10:53:38.27 --- - - - - *** stop SWS to play to see what int times
saturate when close to sun
10:53:38.30 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:54:48.30 SWS 6F - - - - Telescope position set to 6F
10:54:52.77 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:55:09.26 SWS 6F - - - - Telescope position set to 6F
10:55:20.96 LSH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:55:23.05 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:55:36.43 USH - - - - Idling
10:55:36.43 SWS - - - - Idling
10:55:36.45 LSH - - - - Idling
10:55:40.86 SWS - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 100ms.
10:55:43.88 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
10:55:47.81 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:55:47.81 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:55:47.83 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:55:49.50 SWS - - - - Idling
10:55:49.64 LSH - - - - Idling
10:55:49.67 USH - - - - Idling
10:55:51.93 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:55:51.94 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:55:51.94 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:55:53.37 SWS - - - - Idling
10:55:53.57 LSH - - - - Idling
10:55:53.77 USH - - - - Idling
10:55:56.81 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.

```

10:55:56.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:55:56.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:03:19.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:03:19.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:03:19.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:03:21.93	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:03:27.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:03:27.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:03:27.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:03:28.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:03:28.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:03:29.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:03:30.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:03:30.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:03:30.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:03:31.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:03:32.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:03:32.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:03:35.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:03:35.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:03:35.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:03:39.88	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:03:44.33	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:03:46.17	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:04:11.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:04:11.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:04:11.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:04:14.87	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:04:20.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:04:20.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:04:20.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:04:22.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:04:22.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:04:22.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:04:27.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:04:27.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:04:27.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:04:37.57	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:04:38.35	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:04:38.99	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:11:29.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:11:29.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:11:29.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:11:35.20	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:11:40.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:11:42.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:11:43.80	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:11:45.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:11:48.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:11:48.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:11:48.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:11:53.42	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:11:54.15	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:11:54.66	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:12:20.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:12:45.72	---	-	-	-	-	*** m +8
11:12:45.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:12:55.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:12:56.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:16:41.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:16:54.30	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:17:00.25	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:17:01.23	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:17:05.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:17:09.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:17:10.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:19:22.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:19:22.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:19:22.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling

11:19:25.73	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:19:31.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:19:31.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:19:31.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:19:32.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:19:33.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:19:33.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:19:35.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:19:35.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:19:35.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:19:36.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:19:37.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:19:37.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:19:40.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:19:40.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:19:40.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:19:47.53	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:19:48.12	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:19:48.92	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:21:47.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:21:54.19	SWS	-	-	45	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 45ms.
11:21:58.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:22:00.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:22:01.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:22:03.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:22:07.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:22:14.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:22:15.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:22:19.36	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 45ms to 75ms.
11:22:23.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:22:24.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:22:26.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:22:28.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:22:30.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:22:37.77	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:22:43.67	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:22:44.46	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:25:21.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:25:24.42	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 50ms.
11:25:26.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:25:28.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:25:29.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:25:30.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:25:31.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:25:34.52	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:25:35.70	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:25:36.65	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:28:08.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:28:08.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:28:08.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:28:11.14	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:28:16.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:28:16.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:28:16.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:28:17.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:28:17.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:28:17.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:28:19.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:28:19.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:28:19.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:28:20.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:28:21.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:28:21.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:28:21.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:28:21.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:28:21.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:28:23.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:28:23.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:28:23.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling

11:28:24.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:28:24.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:28:24.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:28:29.20	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:28:29.85	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:28:30.41	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:28:52.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:29:10.80	---	-	-	-	-	*** m +8
11:29:10.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:29:14.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:29:15.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:32:36.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:32:40.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:32:42.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:33:03.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:33:04.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:33:05.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:33:07.73	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:33:08.57	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:33:09.49	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:33:10.60	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:34:43.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:34:43.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:34:43.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:34:46.33	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:34:51.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:34:51.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:34:51.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:34:53.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:34:53.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:34:53.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:34:54.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:34:54.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:34:54.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:34:56.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:34:56.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:34:56.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:34:57.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:34:57.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:34:57.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:34:58.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:34:58.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:34:59.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:35:00.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:35:00.74	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:35:00.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:35:02.91	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:35:03.75	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:35:04.24	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:36:41.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:36:41.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:36:41.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:36:43.86	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:36:47.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:36:47.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:36:47.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:36:49.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:36:49.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:36:49.80	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:36:52.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:36:52.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:36:52.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:36:53.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:36:54.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:36:54.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:36:57.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:36:57.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:36:57.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:37:08.46	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F

11:37:09.13	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:37:09.47	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:43:17.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:43:17.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:43:17.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:43:19.13	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:43:23.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:43:23.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:43:23.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:43:25.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:43:25.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:43:25.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:43:26.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:43:26.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:43:26.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:43:27.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:43:28.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:43:28.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:43:28.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:43:28.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:43:28.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:43:30.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:43:30.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:43:30.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:43:31.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:43:31.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:43:31.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:43:34.05	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:43:34.60	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:43:35.05	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:44:45.77	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:45:05.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:45:05.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:45:05.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:45:07.53	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:45:14.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:45:16.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:45:20.82	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:45:26.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:45:28.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:45:32.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:45:33.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:45:37.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:45:38.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:45:41.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:45:41.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:45:41.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:45:43.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:45:43.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:45:43.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:45:44.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:45:44.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:45:44.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:45:45.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:45:46.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:45:46.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:45:47.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:45:47.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:45:47.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:45:48.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:45:48.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:45:48.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:45:49.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:45:49.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:45:49.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:45:50.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:45:51.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:45:51.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:45:53.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

11:45:53.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:45:53.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:45:59.46	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:46:00.03	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:46:00.43	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:47:19.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:47:19.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:47:19.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:47:23.33	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:47:28.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:47:28.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:47:28.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:47:29.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:47:29.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:47:30.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:47:30.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:47:30.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:47:30.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:47:32.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:47:32.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:47:32.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:47:33.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:47:33.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:47:33.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:47:34.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:47:35.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:47:35.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:47:35.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:47:35.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:47:35.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:47:37.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:47:37.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:47:37.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:47:39.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:47:39.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:47:39.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:47:41.57	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:47:42.11	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:47:42.45	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:50:07.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:50:07.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:50:07.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:50:09.54	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:50:14.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:50:14.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:50:14.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:50:15.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:50:16.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:50:16.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:50:17.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:50:17.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:50:17.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:50:18.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:50:18.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:50:19.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:50:23.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:50:23.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:50:23.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:50:26.99	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:50:27.57	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:50:27.96	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:59:06.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:59:06.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:59:06.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:59:08.33	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:59:12.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:59:12.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:59:12.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:59:13.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling

11:59:13.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:59:14.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:59:15.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:59:15.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:59:15.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:59:16.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:59:17.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:59:17.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:59:18.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:59:18.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:59:18.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:59:19.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:59:19.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:59:19.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:59:22.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:59:22.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:59:22.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:59:24.80	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:59:25.29	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:59:25.63	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:04:26.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:04:26.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:04:26.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:04:29.87	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
12:04:34.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:04:34.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:04:34.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:04:35.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:04:35.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:04:35.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:04:37.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:04:37.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:04:37.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:04:38.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:04:38.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:04:38.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:04:39.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:04:39.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:04:39.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:04:40.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:04:41.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:04:41.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:04:42.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:04:42.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:04:42.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:04:44.94	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:04:45.41	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:04:45.74	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:06:05.46	---	-	-	-	-	*** m +6
12:06:16.48	---	-	-	-	-	*** m +6
12:06:40.89	---	-	-	-	-	*** m +6
12:08:32.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:08:32.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:08:32.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:08:36.69	SWS	-	-	25	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 25ms.
12:08:41.31	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
12:08:45.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:08:45.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:08:45.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:08:47.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:08:47.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:08:47.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:08:48.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:08:48.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:08:48.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:08:50.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:08:50.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:08:50.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:08:51.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

12:08:51.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:08:51.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:08:52.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:08:52.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:08:52.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:08:53.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:08:53.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:08:53.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:09:02.08	---	-	-	-	-	*** m +6
12:09:17.37	---	-	-	-	-	*** m +6
12:09:23.41	---	-	-	-	-	*** m +6
12:10:33.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:10:43.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:10:46.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:10:59.44	---	-	-	-	-	*** m -050
12:10:59.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:11:00.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:11:02.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:11:40.50	---	-	-	-	-	*** m -40
12:11:40.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:11:49.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:11:50.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:11:50.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:12:16.46	---	-	-	-	-	*** m -30
12:12:16.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:12:22.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:12:23.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:12:23.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:12:46.38	---	-	-	-	-	*** m -20
12:12:46.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:12:53.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:12:54.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:13:17.75	---	-	-	-	-	*** m -10
12:13:17.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:13:23.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:13:24.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:13:25.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:13:45.90	---	-	-	-	-	*** m 0
12:13:45.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:13:52.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:13:53.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:13:53.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:14:14.43	---	-	-	-	-	*** m +10
12:14:14.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:14:22.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:14:23.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:14:27.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:14:45.34	---	-	-	-	-	*** m +20
12:14:45.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:14:52.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:14:53.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:14:53.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:15:16.36	---	-	-	-	-	*** m +30
12:15:16.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:15:22.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:15:22.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:15:23.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:15:45.07	---	-	-	-	-	*** m +40
12:15:45.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:15:47.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:15:53.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:15:54.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:15:56.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:16:16.30	---	-	-	-	-	*** m +50
12:16:16.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:16:25.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:16:25.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:16:29.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:16:42.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling

12:16:42.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:16:42.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:16:43.94	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
12:16:49.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:16:49.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:16:49.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:16:50.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:16:50.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:16:51.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:16:52.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:16:52.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:16:52.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:16:53.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:16:53.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:16:54.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:17:23.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:17:23.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:17:23.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:17:25.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:17:25.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:17:25.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:17:26.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:17:26.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:17:26.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:17:27.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:17:27.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:17:28.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:17:28.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:17:28.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:17:28.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:17:29.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:17:30.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:17:30.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:17:31.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:17:31.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:17:31.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:17:33.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:17:33.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:17:33.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:17:34.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:17:34.52	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:17:34.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:17:35.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:17:36.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:17:36.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:17:51.54	---	-	-	-	-	*** m +50
12:17:51.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:17:51.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:17:51.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:18:06.47	---	-	-	-	-	*** m +50
12:18:15.97	---	-	-	-	-	*** m +50
12:18:25.54	---	-	-	-	-	*** m +50
12:18:36.73	SWS	-	-	10	-	VIS int.time changed from 25ms to 10ms.
12:18:40.09	SWS	-	-	-	35	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 35ms.
12:18:44.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:18:46.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:18:47.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:18:55.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:18:56.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:19:04.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:19:17.35	---	-	-	-	-	*** m +40
12:19:17.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:19:18.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:19:19.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:19:44.32	---	-	-	-	-	*** m +35
12:19:44.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:19:51.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:19:51.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:19:52.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

12:20:10.92	---	-	-	-	*** m +30
12:20:11.05	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:20:17.42	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:20:18.29	SWS	-	-	-	Idling
12:20:19.52	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:20:38.26	---	-	-	-	*** m +25
12:20:38.37	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:20:46.96	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:20:47.53	SWS	-	-	-	Idling
12:20:48.23	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:21:25.11	---	-	-	-	*** m +20
12:21:25.23	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:21:32.17	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:21:33.61	SWS	-	-	-	Idling
12:21:34.66	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:21:54.94	SWS	-	-	-	Idling
12:21:55.00	LSH	-	-	-	Idling
12:21:55.00	USH	-	-	-	Idling
12:21:56.57	---	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
12:22:01.80	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:22:01.80	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:22:01.81	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:22:02.60	SWS	-	-	-	Idling
12:22:03.44	LSH	-	-	-	Idling
12:22:03.64	USH	-	-	-	Idling
12:22:04.50	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:22:04.51	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:22:04.52	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:22:05.30	SWS	-	-	-	Idling
12:22:06.15	LSH	-	-	-	Idling
12:22:06.34	USH	-	-	-	Idling
12:22:06.88	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:22:06.89	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:22:06.89	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:22:07.67	SWS	-	-	-	Idling
12:22:08.52	LSH	-	-	-	Idling
12:22:08.73	USH	-	-	-	Idling
12:22:09.53	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:22:09.53	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:22:09.54	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:22:10.33	SWS	-	-	-	Idling
12:22:11.16	LSH	-	-	-	Idling
12:22:11.36	USH	-	-	-	Idling
12:22:51.20	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:22:51.20	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:22:51.21	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:22:52.39	SWS	-	-	-	Idling
12:22:52.66	USH	-	-	-	Idling
12:22:52.83	LSH	-	-	-	Idling
12:22:53.15	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:22:53.15	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:22:53.16	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:22:54.34	SWS	-	-	-	Idling
12:22:54.60	USH	-	-	-	Idling
12:22:54.68	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:22:54.68	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:22:54.79	LSH	-	-	-	Idling
12:22:54.81	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:22:55.46	SWS	-	-	-	Idling
12:22:56.08	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:22:56.31	USH	-	-	-	Idling
12:22:56.51	LSH	-	-	-	Idling
12:22:56.89	SWS	-	-	-	Idling
12:23:01.42	SWS	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 35ms to 100ms.
12:23:04.79	SWS	-	-	100	VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 100ms.
12:23:07.03	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:23:07.03	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:23:07.05	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:23:08.90	USH	-	-	-	Idling

12:23:09.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:23:09.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:23:09.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:23:09.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:23:09.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:23:11.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:23:11.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:23:11.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:23:12.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:23:12.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:23:12.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:23:13.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:23:13.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:23:14.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:23:14.80	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:23:14.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:23:14.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:23:16.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:23:16.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:23:16.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:23:16.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:23:17.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:23:17.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:23:18.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:23:18.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:23:18.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:23:19.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:23:19.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:23:19.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:23:20.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:23:20.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:23:21.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:23:21.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:23:21.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:23:21.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:23:23.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:23:23.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:23:23.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:23:26.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:23:27.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:23:27.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:23:29.98	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:23:30.69	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:23:31.26	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:28:13.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:13.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:13.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:15.13	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
12:28:18.34	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
12:28:22.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:28:22.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:28:22.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:28:23.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:24.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:24.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:25.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:28:25.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:28:25.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:28:26.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:27.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:27.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:27.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:28:27.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:28:27.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:28:29.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:29.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:29.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:30.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:28:30.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

12:28:30.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:28:31.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:31.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:31.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:32.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:28:32.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:28:32.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:28:34.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:34.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:34.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:34.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:28:34.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:28:35.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:28:36.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:36.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:36.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:37.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:28:37.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:28:37.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:28:41.12	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:28:41.55	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:28:41.87	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:33:44.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:33:44.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:33:44.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:33:46.00	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
12:33:49.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:33:49.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:33:49.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:33:51.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:33:51.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:33:51.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:33:52.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:33:52.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:33:52.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:33:53.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:33:53.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:33:54.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:33:54.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:33:54.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:33:54.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:33:56.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:33:56.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:33:56.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:33:56.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:33:56.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:33:56.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:33:58.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:33:58.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:33:58.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:33:59.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:33:59.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:33:59.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:34:00.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:34:00.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:34:01.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:34:01.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:34:01.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:34:01.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:34:03.97	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:34:04.44	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:34:04.75	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:36:22.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:36:47.60	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
12:36:50.52	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
12:36:51.78	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
12:36:54.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:36:55.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:36:55.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

12:37:31.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:37:52.66	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:37:53.63	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:37:54.60	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:37:57.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:37:57.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:37:58.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:38:24.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:38:24.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:38:24.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:38:27.94	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 75ms.
12:38:29.89	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
12:38:33.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:38:33.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:38:33.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:38:35.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:38:35.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:38:35.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:38:35.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:38:35.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:38:35.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:38:36.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:38:37.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:38:37.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:38:37.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:38:37.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:38:37.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:38:39.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:38:39.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:38:39.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:38:40.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:38:40.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:38:40.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:38:42.19	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:38:42.92	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:38:43.48	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:43:01.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:43:01.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:43:01.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:43:03.96	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
12:43:09.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:43:09.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:43:09.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:43:11.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:43:11.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:43:11.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:43:12.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:43:12.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:43:12.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:43:13.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:43:13.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:43:14.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:43:14.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:43:14.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:43:14.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:43:16.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:43:16.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:43:16.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:43:17.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:43:17.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:43:17.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:43:18.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:43:18.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:43:19.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:43:20.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:43:20.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:43:20.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:43:21.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:43:21.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling

12:43:22.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:43:23.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:43:23.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:43:23.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:43:25.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:43:25.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:43:25.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:43:27.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:43:27.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:43:27.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:43:28.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:43:28.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:43:28.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:43:30.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:43:30.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:43:30.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:43:31.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:43:32.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:43:32.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:43:33.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:43:33.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:43:33.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:43:35.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:43:35.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:43:35.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:43:38.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:43:38.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:43:38.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:43:39.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:43:39.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:43:40.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:43:42.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:43:42.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:43:42.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:43:44.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:43:44.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:43:44.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:43:47.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:43:47.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:43:47.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:43:48.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:43:48.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:43:48.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:43:51.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:43:51.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:43:51.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:43:52.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:43:53.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:43:53.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:43:55.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:44:04.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:44:04.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:44:11.63	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:44:12.36	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:44:12.86	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:44:58.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:45:02.14	SWS	-	-	30	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 30ms.
12:45:04.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:45:05.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:45:07.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:45:10.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:45:11.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:45:13.96	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:45:14.96	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:45:16.31	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:46:56.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:47:00.65	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 75ms.
12:47:02.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:47:04.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!

12:47:04.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:47:06.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:47:07.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:47:10.87	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:47:12.30	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:47:13.77	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:47:32.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:47:32.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:47:32.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:47:36.10	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
12:47:40.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:47:40.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:47:40.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:47:41.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:47:41.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:47:42.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:47:43.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:47:43.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:47:43.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:47:44.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:47:44.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:47:45.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:47:45.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:47:45.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:47:45.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:47:47.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:47:47.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:47:47.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:47:47.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:47:47.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:47:47.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:47:49.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:47:49.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:47:49.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:47:50.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:47:50.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:47:50.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:47:51.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:47:51.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:47:51.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:47:52.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:47:52.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:47:52.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:47:53.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:47:53.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:47:54.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:47:54.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:47:54.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:47:54.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:47:55.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:47:56.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:47:56.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:47:56.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:47:56.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:47:56.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:47:57.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:47:58.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:47:58.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:47:59.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:48:01.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:48:01.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:48:04.00	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:48:04.56	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:48:04.95	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:52:51.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:52:51.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:52:51.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:52:53.61	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
12:52:57.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

12:52:57.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:52:57.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:52:59.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:52:59.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:52:59.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:53:00.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:53:00.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:53:00.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:53:02.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:53:02.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:53:02.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:53:03.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:53:03.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:53:03.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:53:06.03	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:53:06.55	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:53:06.89	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:55:36.19	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:58:56.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:58:56.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:58:56.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:59:00.31	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
12:59:05.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:59:05.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:59:05.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:59:06.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:59:06.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:59:06.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:59:07.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:59:07.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:59:07.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:59:09.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:59:09.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:59:09.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:59:10.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:59:10.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:59:10.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:59:11.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:59:11.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:59:12.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:59:13.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:59:13.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:59:13.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:59:14.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:59:14.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:59:14.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:59:16.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:59:19.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:59:19.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:59:25.45	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:59:25.80	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:59:26.14	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
13:03:53.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:04:10.68	---	-	-	-	-	*** m +8
13:04:10.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:04:12.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:04:12.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:04:27.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:04:45.94	---	-	-	-	-	*** m -174
13:04:48.03	SWS	-	-	40	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 40ms.
13:04:51.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:04:53.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:04:55.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:04:56.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:04:59.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:05:43.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:06:05.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:06:05.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:06:05.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling

13:06:06.90	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
13:06:13.09	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 40ms to 75ms.
13:06:14.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:06:14.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:06:14.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:06:16.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:06:16.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:06:16.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:06:17.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:06:17.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:06:17.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:06:19.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:06:19.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:06:19.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:06:21.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:06:21.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:06:21.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:06:22.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:06:22.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:06:22.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:06:33.65	---	-	-	-	-	*** m +8
13:06:33.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:06:33.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:06:33.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:07:08.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:07:17.70	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
13:07:20.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:07:21.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:07:22.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:07:24.33	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
13:07:24.78	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
13:07:25.16	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
13:08:45.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:08:45.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:08:45.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:08:47.42	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
13:08:51.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:08:51.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:08:51.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:08:53.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:08:53.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:08:53.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:08:54.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:08:54.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:08:54.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:08:55.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:08:55.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:08:56.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:08:56.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:08:56.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:08:56.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:08:57.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:08:57.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:08:58.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:09:01.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:09:01.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:09:01.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:09:13.29	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
13:09:14.01	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
13:09:14.38	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
13:13:59.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:13:59.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:13:59.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:14:01.63	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
13:14:05.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:14:06.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:14:07.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:14:11.55	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
13:14:12.15	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F

13:14:12.85	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
13:17:21.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:17:32.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:17:35.43	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
13:17:36.90	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
13:17:37.49	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
13:17:57.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:18:00.09	SWS	-	-	40	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 40ms.
13:18:01.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:18:36.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:18:38.52	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
13:18:42.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:18:42.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:18:42.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:18:44.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:18:44.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:18:44.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:18:45.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:18:45.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:18:45.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:18:46.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:18:47.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:18:47.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:18:50.10	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 40ms to 75ms.
13:18:51.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:18:51.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:18:51.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:18:53.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:18:53.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:18:53.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:18:54.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:18:54.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:18:54.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:18:55.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:18:56.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:18:56.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:19:12.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:19:12.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:19:12.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:19:15.97	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
13:19:16.49	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
13:19:16.91	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
13:21:48.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:21:52.79	SWS	-	-	35	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 35ms.
13:22:07.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:22:08.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:22:09.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:22:11.20	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
13:22:11.74	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
13:22:12.36	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
13:23:38.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:23:38.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:23:38.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:23:40.69	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
13:23:45.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:23:45.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:23:45.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:23:46.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:23:46.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:23:46.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:23:48.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:23:48.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:23:48.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:23:49.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:23:49.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:23:49.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:23:53.31	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 35ms to 75ms.
13:23:55.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:23:55.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

13:23:55.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:23:56.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:23:56.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:23:57.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:23:57.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:23:57.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:23:57.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:23:59.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:23:59.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:23:59.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:24:14.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:24:14.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:24:14.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:24:17.61	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
13:24:18.43	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
13:24:19.01	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
13:26:15.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:26:18.67	SWS	-	-	45	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 45ms.
13:26:30.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:26:33.26	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
13:26:33.92	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
13:26:34.61	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
13:27:24.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:27:24.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:27:24.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:27:26.13	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
13:27:30.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:27:30.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:27:30.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:27:31.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:27:31.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:27:31.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:27:32.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:27:32.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:27:32.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:27:34.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:27:34.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:27:34.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:27:36.72	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 45ms to 75ms.
13:27:38.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:27:38.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:27:38.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:27:40.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:27:40.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:27:40.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:27:40.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:27:40.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:27:40.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:27:42.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:27:42.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:27:42.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:27:53.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:27:53.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:27:53.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:27:55.76	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
13:27:56.59	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
13:27:57.23	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
13:28:54.19	---	-	-	-	-	*** m +4
13:28:54.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:29:01.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:29:02.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:29:03.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:30:10.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:30:10.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:30:10.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:30:12.23	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
13:30:16.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:30:16.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:30:16.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

13:30:17.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:30:17.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:30:17.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:30:18.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:30:18.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:30:18.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:30:19.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:30:20.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:30:20.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:30:21.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:30:21.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:30:21.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:30:22.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:30:23.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:30:23.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:30:24.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:30:24.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:30:24.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:30:35.82	---	-	-	-	-	*** m +4
13:30:35.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:30:36.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:30:38.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:30:39.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:31:04.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:31:06.74	SWS	-	-	35	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 35ms.
13:31:09.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:31:10.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:31:11.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:31:13.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:31:20.36	---	-	-	-	-	*** m +4
13:31:20.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:31:23.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:31:24.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:34:29.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:34:31.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:34:32.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:34:33.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:34:35.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:34:48.52	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
13:35:07.07	SWS	-	500	-	-	Sample period changed from 100ms to 500ms.
13:35:10.85	SWS	-	100	-	-	Sample period changed from 500ms to 100ms.
13:36:31.01	---	-	-	-	-	
13:36:31.01	---	-	-	-	-	+++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
13:36:31.01	---	-	-	-	-	+++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period / tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
13:36:31.01	---	-	-	-	-	+++ Flight no. B324
13:36:31.01	---	-	-	-	-	
13:36:42.65	SWS	-	100	-	-	Sample period changed from 500ms to 100ms.
13:36:42.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
13:36:42.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
13:36:43.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
13:36:47.04	USH	-	100	-	-	Sample period changed from 500ms to 100ms.
13:36:51.28	LSH	-	100	-	-	Sample period changed from 500ms to 100ms.
13:36:56.72	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 75ms.
13:37:01.22	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
13:37:08.06	USH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
13:37:11.95	USH	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
13:37:17.54	LSH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
13:37:21.36	LSH	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
13:37:26.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:37:26.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:37:26.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:37:29.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:37:29.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:37:29.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:37:33.92	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
13:37:37.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:37:37.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:37:37.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

13:37:38.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:37:38.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:37:39.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:37:40.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:37:40.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:37:40.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:37:51.48	---	-	-	-	-	*** m +4
13:37:51.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:37:52.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:39:28.63	---	-	-	-	-	*** LabView lost focus on al SWS buttons. Shut it down and restarted, regained controll
13:39:28.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:39:29.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:40:59.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:41:14.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:41:27.47	---	-	-	-	-	*** m -176
13:41:27.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:41:28.24	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:42:07.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:42:07.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:42:07.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:42:09.32	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
13:42:14.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:42:14.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:42:14.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:42:15.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:42:15.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:42:16.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:42:17.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:42:17.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:42:17.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:42:18.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:42:18.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:42:18.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:42:20.81	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 100ms.
13:42:22.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:42:22.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:42:22.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:42:23.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:42:24.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:42:24.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:42:24.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:42:24.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:42:24.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:42:26.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:42:26.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:42:26.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:42:39.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:42:39.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:42:39.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:42:51.09	---	-	-	-	-	*** m +4
13:42:51.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:42:52.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:43:04.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:43:11.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:43:13.00	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
13:47:05.90	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
13:47:06.59	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
13:47:36.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:47:50.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:47:52.89	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
13:47:53.86	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
13:48:11.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:48:13.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:48:15.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:48:17.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:48:19.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:48:20.31	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
13:48:25.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

13:48:26.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:48:30.72	SWS	-	-	40	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 40ms.
13:48:33.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:48:40.72	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
13:48:47.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:48:50.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:48:52.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:48:54.57	SWS	-	-	25	-	VIS int.time changed from 40ms to 25ms.
13:48:56.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:48:59.09	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
13:49:06.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:49:06.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:49:06.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:49:08.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:49:08.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:49:08.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:49:09.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:49:10.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:49:10.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:49:11.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:49:11.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:49:11.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:49:12.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:49:12.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:49:13.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:49:18.93	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 25ms to 100ms.
13:49:37.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:49:37.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:49:37.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:49:38.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:49:38.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:49:38.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:49:39.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:49:39.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:49:39.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:49:46.78	---	-	-	-	-	*** m +5
13:49:46.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:49:47.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:52:07.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:52:20.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:52:23.29	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
13:52:33.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:52:33.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:52:34.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:52:35.46	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
13:52:39.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:52:39.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:52:39.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:52:40.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:52:40.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:52:40.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:52:44.51	SWS	-	-	40	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 40ms.
13:52:45.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:52:45.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:52:45.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:52:47.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:52:47.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:52:48.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:52:49.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:52:49.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:52:49.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:52:50.95	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
13:54:06.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:54:06.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:54:06.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:54:08.52	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
13:54:12.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:54:12.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:54:12.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

13:54:14.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:54:14.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:54:14.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:54:16.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:54:16.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:54:16.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:54:17.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:54:17.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:54:17.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:54:19.99	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 40ms to 100ms.
13:54:22.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:54:22.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:54:22.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:54:24.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:54:24.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:54:25.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:54:26.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:54:26.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:54:26.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:54:27.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:54:27.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:54:27.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:54:42.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:54:42.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:54:42.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:54:49.59	---	-	-	-	-	*** m +4
13:54:49.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:54:50.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:54:51.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:54:52.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:57:41.92	---	-	-	-	-	*** m +4
13:57:42.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:57:42.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:01:06.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:01:06.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:01:06.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:01:09.08	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
14:01:13.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:01:13.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:01:13.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:01:14.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:01:15.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:01:15.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:01:16.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:01:16.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:01:16.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:01:17.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:01:17.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:01:17.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:01:27.59	---	-	-	-	-	*** m +4
14:01:27.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:01:27.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:01:27.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:01:49.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:01:57.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:02:06.84	---	-	-	-	-	*** m -176
14:02:06.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:02:29.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:02:57.63	---	-	-	-	-	*** m +4
14:02:57.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:03:58.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:03:58.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:03:58.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:04:00.82	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
14:04:05.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:04:05.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:04:05.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:04:06.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:04:06.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling

14:04:07.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:04:07.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:04:07.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:04:07.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:04:08.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:04:09.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:04:09.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:04:09.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:04:09.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:04:09.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:04:11.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:04:11.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:04:11.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:04:24.59	---	-	-	-	-	*** m +4
14:04:24.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:04:24.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:04:24.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:05:36.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:05:36.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:05:36.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:05:38.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:05:38.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:05:38.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:05:39.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:05:39.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:05:39.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:05:40.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:05:40.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:05:40.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:05:42.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:05:42.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:05:42.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:05:48.07	SWS	-	-	30	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 30ms.
14:05:51.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:05:51.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:05:51.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:05:52.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:05:52.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:05:53.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:05:53.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:05:53.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:05:53.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:05:55.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:05:55.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:05:55.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:06:22.08	---	-	-	-	-	*** m -176
14:06:22.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:06:22.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:06:22.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:10:29.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:10:29.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:10:29.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:10:31.36	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
14:10:35.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:10:35.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:10:35.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:10:37.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:10:37.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:10:37.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:10:38.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:10:38.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:10:38.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:10:39.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:10:40.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:10:40.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:10:40.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:10:40.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:10:41.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:10:42.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling

14:10:42.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:10:42.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:10:45.50	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 100ms.
14:10:46.80	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:10:46.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:10:46.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:10:48.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:10:48.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:10:48.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:10:49.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:10:49.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:10:49.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:10:50.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:10:50.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:10:50.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:11:08.72	---	-	-	-	-	*** m +4
14:11:08.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:11:08.74	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:11:08.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:14:12.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:14:38.26	SWS	-	-	30	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 30ms.
14:14:49.26	---	-	-	-	-	*** m -176
14:14:49.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:15:09.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:15:09.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:15:09.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:15:10.89	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
14:15:14.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:15:14.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:15:14.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:15:16.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:15:16.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:15:16.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:15:17.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:15:17.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:15:17.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:15:18.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:15:19.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:15:19.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:15:23.67	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 100ms.
14:15:24.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:15:24.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:15:24.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:15:26.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:15:26.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:15:26.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:15:27.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:15:27.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:15:27.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:15:28.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:15:29.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:15:29.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:15:49.27	---	-	-	-	-	*** m +4
14:15:49.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:15:49.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:15:49.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:19:01.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:01.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:01.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:07.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:19:07.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:19:07.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:19:08.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:08.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:09.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:13.47	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
14:19:23.83	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
14:19:26.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:19:26.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

```

14:37:03.31 --- - - - - *** !!!174R at 14:30;09:33 should be 6F!!!
14:37:03.39 LSH - - - - Idling
14:37:04.48 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:37:29.02 LSH - - - - Idling
14:37:29.02 USH - - - - Idling
14:37:29.10 SWS - - - - Idling
14:37:30.66 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
14:37:34.74 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:37:34.74 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:37:34.76 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:37:36.17 SWS - - - - Idling
14:37:36.37 LSH - - - - Idling
14:37:36.57 USH - - - - Idling
14:37:38.28 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:37:38.28 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:37:38.30 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:37:39.87 LSH - - - - Idling
14:37:39.91 USH - - - - Idling
14:37:40.13 SWS - - - - Idling
14:37:57.25 SWS 6F - - - - Telescope position set to 6F
14:37:59.49 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:37:59.49 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:37:59.50 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:40:03.45 SWS - - - - Idling
14:40:03.46 USH - - - - Idling
14:40:03.50 LSH - - - - Idling
14:40:18.65 SWS 174R - - - - Telescope position set to 174R
14:40:22.49 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:40:22.49 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:40:22.50 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:41:37.58 SWS - - - - Idling
14:41:37.64 LSH - - - - Idling
14:41:37.66 USH - - - - Idling
14:41:40.36 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
14:41:44.57 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:41:44.58 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:41:44.58 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:41:46.01 LSH - - - - Idling
14:41:46.21 USH - - - - Idling
14:41:46.42 SWS - - - - Idling
14:41:47.25 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:41:47.25 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:41:47.27 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:41:48.68 SWS - - - - Idling
14:41:48.92 USH - - - - Idling
14:41:49.09 LSH - - - - Idling
14:42:07.06 SWS 6F - - - - Telescope position set to 6F
14:42:11.01 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:42:14.10 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:42:14.10 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:42:26.66 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:42:31.58 SWS - - 300 - VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 300ms.
14:42:35.48 SWS - - 200 - NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
14:42:38.08 SWS - - 200 - VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 200ms.
14:42:41.27 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:42:43.94 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:42:44.86 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:42:47.30 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:42:48.22 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:42:53.46 SWS 6F - - - - Telescope position set to 6F
14:45:55.73 SWS - - - - Idling
14:45:55.81 LSH - - - - Idling
14:45:55.83 USH - - - - Idling
14:45:57.48 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
14:46:01.72 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:46:01.72 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:46:01.73 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:46:03.35 LSH - - - - Idling
14:46:03.55 USH - - - - Idling

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14:46:04.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:46:05.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:46:05.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:46:05.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:46:07.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:46:07.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:46:08.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:46:11.91	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
14:46:15.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:46:15.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:46:15.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:48:03.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:48:03.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:48:03.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:48:07.03	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
14:48:10.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:48:10.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:48:10.80	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:48:12.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:48:12.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:48:13.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:48:13.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:48:14.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:48:14.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:48:15.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:48:15.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:48:16.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:48:17.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:48:17.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:48:17.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:48:20.72	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
14:50:38.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:50:38.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:50:38.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:50:40.06	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
14:50:43.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:50:43.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:50:43.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:50:45.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:50:45.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:50:46.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:50:46.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:50:46.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:50:46.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:50:48.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:50:48.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:50:49.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:50:53.23	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
14:50:55.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:50:55.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:50:55.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:53:49.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:53:49.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:53:49.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:53:51.73	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
14:53:55.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:53:55.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:53:55.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:53:56.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:53:56.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:53:57.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:53:58.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:53:58.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:53:58.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:53:59.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:53:59.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:54:00.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:54:00.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:54:01.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling

14:54:18.00	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
14:54:19.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:54:19.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:54:19.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:54:57.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:54:57.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:54:57.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:55:00.31	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
14:55:05.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:55:05.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:55:05.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:55:06.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:55:06.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:55:07.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:55:08.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:55:08.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:55:09.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:55:10.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:55:10.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:55:11.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:55:23.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:55:23.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:55:23.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:55:25.41	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
14:58:12.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:58:12.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:58:12.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:58:15.40	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
14:58:19.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:58:19.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:58:19.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:58:20.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:58:21.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:58:21.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:58:21.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:58:21.74	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:58:21.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:58:23.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:58:23.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:58:24.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:58:33.96	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
14:58:36.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:58:36.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:58:36.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:58:42.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:58:46.92	SWS	-	-	35	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 35ms.
14:58:49.39	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
14:58:52.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:58:53.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:58:54.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:58:55.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:58:57.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:59:01.63	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
14:59:30.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:59:32.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:59:34.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:59:38.32	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 35ms to 200ms.
14:59:41.69	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
14:59:47.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:59:49.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:59:51.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:59:54.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
15:00:02.27	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
15:00:04.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:02:58.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
15:03:01.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:03:03.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
15:03:07.79	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 75ms.
15:03:11.08	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.

15:03:12.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:03:14.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
15:03:24.85	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
15:03:27.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:03:45.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:03:45.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:03:45.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:03:48.48	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
15:03:52.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:03:52.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:03:52.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:03:53.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:03:54.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:03:54.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:03:54.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:03:54.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:03:54.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:03:56.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:03:56.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:03:56.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:03:59.88	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 200ms.
15:04:02.41	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
15:04:03.74	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:04:03.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:04:03.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:04:05.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:04:05.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:04:06.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:04:06.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:04:07.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:04:08.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:04:08.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:04:16.10	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
15:04:18.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:04:18.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:04:18.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:07:24.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
15:07:26.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:07:28.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
15:07:30.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:07:33.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
15:07:35.56	SWS	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 300ms.
15:07:38.74	SWS	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 400ms.
15:07:40.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:07:45.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
15:07:46.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:07:50.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
15:07:52.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:07:57.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
15:07:59.71	SWS	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 400ms.
15:08:03.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:08:07.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
15:08:08.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:08:13.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
15:08:14.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:09:59.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:09:59.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:10:00.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:10:03.23	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
15:10:19.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:10:19.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:10:19.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:10:21.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:10:21.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:10:24.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:10:25.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:10:25.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:10:25.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:10:26.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling

15:10:27.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:10:30.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:10:32.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:10:32.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:10:32.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:10:34.89	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
15:14:26.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:14:26.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:14:26.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:14:28.60	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
15:14:32.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:14:32.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:14:32.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:14:33.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:14:34.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:14:35.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:14:35.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:14:36.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:14:36.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:14:37.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:14:37.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:14:37.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:14:37.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:14:39.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:14:39.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:14:40.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:14:40.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:14:41.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:14:41.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:14:42.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:14:43.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:14:43.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:14:43.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:14:44.80	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
15:15:48.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:15:48.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:15:48.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:15:59.13	---	-	-	-	-	*** End science
15:16:03.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:16:03.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:16:03.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:16:04.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:16:05.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:16:07.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:16:07.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:16:08.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:16:08.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:16:09.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:16:10.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:16:10.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:16:10.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

ARIES flight log

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Date: 03/SEPT/07 Operator(s): S. ROGERS Res: 1 Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: CHILBOLTON CIRCUITS.

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
08 54 20	—		CH	C	73	31	Script 1 cal (30sec C; 30sec H)
10 40	T/O.						
10 53 30	Tran-	1x60	CH	C	71	31	
10 55 07		240x1	Z	O	71	31	Banking 10:56:32 Ci above.
10 57 14		120x1	N	C	71	31	Banking.
10 58 20		1x60	CH	C	70	30	
10 59 39		240x1	Z	O	71	31	
11 01 51		120x1	N	C	71	31	
11 02 53		1x60	CH	C	71	31	
11 04 08		240x1	Z	O	71	31	
11 06 19		120x1	N	C	71	30	
11 07 24	FL200	1x60	CH	C	71	30	
11 08 39	↑	240x1	Z	O	71	31	
11 10 52		120x1	N	C	71	31	
11 11 56	PI	1x60	CH	C			
11 13 35		240x1	Z	O	71	31	
11 16		120x1	N	C	71	31	
11 16 58	FL240	1x60	CH	C	71	30	
11 18 15		240x1	Z	O	70	30	Closed at start.
11 20 27		120x1	N	C	71	31	
11 21 30		1x60	CH	C	71	31	
11 24 48		240x1	Z	O	71	31	Closed at start
11 27 04		120x1	N	C	71	31	
11 28 07	↑	1x60	CH	C	71	31	
11 52 04	FL310	1x60	CH	C	71	30	
11 53 22		240x1	Z	O	71	31	Ci above. quite thick
11 55 30		120x1	N	C	71	31	
11 56 36		1x60	CH	C	71	30	Ops - interrupted .
57 44		240x1		O			
11 57 44		1x60	CH	C	70	31	
11 59 15		240x1	Z	O	70	30	

ARIES flight log

 Flight: B324

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Date:

Operator(s):

Res:

Gain A: B:

Loc./Notes:

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Sht	HBB	CBB	Comments
12 01 22	FL310	120x1	N	C	71	31	
12 02 27	"	1x60	CH	C	71	30	
12 03 46		240x1	Z	O	71	30	Thick Ci above.
12 06 03		120x1	N	C	71	31	
12 07 06		1x60	CH	C	70	31	Ops - interrupted
12 08 14		1x60	CH	C	70	30	
12 09 38		240x1	Z	O			End of run - aborted view.
12 11 18		1x60	CH	C	70	30	Down-sun
12 12 33		240x1	Z	O	70	30	
12 14 44		120x1	N	C	71	31	
12 15 49		1x60	CH	C	71	31	
12 18 54		1x60	CH	C	71	30	
12 20 09		240x1	Z	O	71	31	Aborted here end - end of run
12 22 07		120x1	N	C	71	31	
12 23 10		1x60	CH	C	71	31	
12 24 23		240x1	Z	O	70	31	
12 26 35		120x1	N	C	71	31	
12 27 38		1x60	CH	C	71	31	
		240x1	Z				
12 35 00	FL340	1x60	CH	C	71	31	
12 36 20		240x1	Z	O	71	31	Ci above. Hazy around.
12 38 30		120x1	N	C	71	31	
12 39 34		1x60	CH	C	71	30	
12 40 -		240x1	Z	O	71	30	Aborted - no progress!
12		240x1	Z	O	71	31	
12 43 15		120x1	N	C	71	30	
12 44 18		1x60	CH	C	71	30	
12 50 41		240x1	Z	C	71	30	
12 51 58	↓	240x1	Z	O	71	30	
12 54 12		120x1	N	C	70	31	
12 55 19		1x60	CH	C	71	31	

ARIES flight log

Flight: 13324

page 3 of 5

Date:

Operator(s):

Res:

Gain A: B:

Loc./Notes:

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
13 01 09	FL350	1x60	CH	C	71	30	
13 02 26		240x1	Z	O	70	30	Ci above.
13 04 38		120x1	N	C	71	31	
13 05 40	↓	1x60	CH	C	71	31	
13 14 04	FL340	1x60	CH	C	71	30	
13 15 29		240x1	Z	O	70	31	Closed at first?
13 17 27		120x1	N	C	71	30	
13 18 31		1x60	CH	C	71	30	
13 19 44		240x1	Z	O	71	30	
13 21 52		120x1	N	C	71	31	
13 22 54		1x60	CH	C	71	31	
13 24 10		240x1	Z	O	71	31	
13 26 20		120x1	N	C	71	31	
13 27 24		1x60	CH	C	71	30	
13 28 36		240x1	Z	O	71	30	Absorted near end - end of run
13 30 20		120x1	N	C	71	31	
13 31 22		1x60	CH	C	71	31	
13 37 38	FL340	1x60	CH	C	71	30	
13 38 54		240x1	Z	O	71	30	
13 41 03		120x1	N	C	71	31	
13 42 06		1x60	CH	C	71	31	
13 44 04	↑ FL350	1x60	CH	C	71	30	
13 45 19		240x1	Z	O	71	30	
13 47 33		120x1	N	C	71	31	
13 48 39		1x60	CH	C	71	30	
13 49 52		240x1	Z	O	71	31	
13 52 05		120x1	N	C	71	31	
13 53 07		1x60	CH	C	71	31	
13 54 21		240x1	Z	O	71	30	
13 56 52		120x1	N	C	71	31	
13 58 00		1x60	CH	C	70	31	

ARIES flight log

 Flight: B324

 page 4 of 5

Date:

Operator(s):

Res:

Gain A: B:

Loc./Notes:

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
135916	FL350	240x1	Z	O	71	30	Patchy cirrhone.
140125		120x1	N	C	71	31	1/8 cu below
140228		1x60	CH	C	70	30	
140615	FL350	1x60	CH	C	71	31	
140727		360x1	N	C	71	30	
141028		1x60	CH	C	71	30	
141145		240x1	Z	O	71	31	
141357		120x1	N	C	71	31	
141504		1x60	CH	C	71	31	
141625		240x1	Z	O	71	31	
141832		120x1	N	C	71	31	
141941	↓	1x60	CH	C	71	31	
142030		1x60	CH	C	71		Didn't start H.?
142103	FL330	1x60	CH	C	71	31	OK
142239	01	240x1	Z	O	71	30	40° orbit. left
142522		1x60	CH	C	71	31	X Operator idiosyncy - interrupted view.
		240x1					
142621	02	1x60	CH	C	71	30	
142726		240x1	Z	O	70	30	
143003		1x60	CH	C	70	31	
143210	FL330	1x60	CH	C	71	31	
143323		240x1	Z	O	71	31	
143531		120x1	N	C	71	30	
143639		1x60	CH	C	71	31	
143755		240x1	Z	O	71	31	
1440-		120x1	N	C	71	31	
144105		1x60	CH	C	70	31	
144219		240x1	Z	O	71	30	
144428		120x1	N	C	71	31	
144531		1x60	CH	C	71	30	
		240x1	Z				

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	03/09/07	Flight	B324	log pages
Operator(s)	Rob King		Campaign	CAESAR/VisUrb		
Departure	Cranfield		Arrival	Cranfield		

System start

MARSS

Visual pod inspection							
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers							
Close all MARSS circuit breakers							
FERA on						at time	08:30:00
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	22°C	Ch	23°C	Ch18	20°C	
Temperature controller set points		54°C	17	58°C	-20	40°C	
MARSS CPU on						at time	08:14:05
Initial target temperatures	Hot	290	Cold				290
Target heating							
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***							
Scanning on (LMD box)						at time	08:18:08
Scan indication	Monitor				Visual		

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers							
Turn on Deimos CPU							
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***							
Start Deimos Software						at time	
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold				
Target heating							
Scan indication	Monitor				Visual		
Weather	Cloud		Precip				
	Surface		Pressure				
	Other						

System functionality check

(after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC}=t_{DRS} +$						at time
Brightness temps 'sensible'							
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	344.76	Cold	289.7		
	Deimos:	Hot	344.91	Cold	303.46		
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B			
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)			
	Ch16 (40-44)	Ch17 (45-49)	Ch18 (40-44)	Ch19 (40-44)	Ch20 (44-48)		
	32.96	31.64	38.66	40.10	42.05		

Power changeover

Headset on before start						
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.					
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)						
Exit Deimos Software (x)						
POWER CHANGEOVER						
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton					
Restart Deimos Software						
System running again						at time

Flight:

B324

KEY

- Duff Data
- Minor Problems
- OK
- Not Fitted
- Fitted, Not Operated

Thermometers

- Cabin Temperature:
- Heimann:
- Deiced Temp:
- Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

- FWVS:
- General Eastern:
- Johnson Williams:
- Nevezorov:
- Total Water Probe:

Cameras

- Downward Facing:
- Forward Facing:
- Rearward Facing:
- Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

- Cruciform GPS:
- GIN Applanix:
- INU Honeywell:
- Radar Altimeter:
- RVSM IAS:
- RVSM Static Pressure:
- XR5 GPS:

Report Created 04/09/2007
15:46:43

Misc Core

- AMTG:
- AVAPS:
- Cabin Pressure:
- Fax machine:
- Printer:
- S9 Static Pressure:
- Satcom C:
- Satcom H:
- Turb Centre-Static:
- Turb Left Right:
- Turb Up-Down:
- Turb Horizontal Chk:
- Turb Vertical Chk:
- Weather Radar:
- DLUs:**
- DLU AERACK:
- DLU BBR Lower:
- DLU BBR Upper:
- DLU Core Chem:
- DLU Core Consoles:
- DLU Port Aft:
- DLU Port Fwd:
- DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

- Lower:**
- BBR (clear) Lower:
- BBR (IR) Lower:
- BBR (red) Lower:
- Upper:**
- BBR (clear) Upper:
- BBR (IR) Upper:
- BBR (red) Upper:
- ARIES:
- DEIMOS:
- IR Camera:
- JNO2 Lower:
- JNO2 Upper:
- JO1D Lower:
- JO1D Upper:
- MARSS:
- SHIMS Lower:
- SHIMS Upper:
- SWS:
- TAFTS:

Last Updated:

Cloud Probes

- 2DC:
- 2DP:
- FFSSP:
- PCASP:
- ADA:
- CCN:
- CDP:
- CIP 100:
- CIP 25:
- CPI:
- CVI:
- SID1:
- SID2:
- Aerosol**
- CPC 3025A:
- Filters 47mm:
- Filters 90mm:
- Neph - Dry:
- Neph - Wet:
- PSAP:
- AMS:
- CPC 3025 (AMS):
- INC:
- VACC:
- CPC 3010A (CVI):

04/09/2007 11:04:03

Chemistry

- CO Aerolaser 5002:
- NOx TE42C:
- Ozone TE49C:
- Ozone TE49:
- SO2 TE43C:
- TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
- TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
- FAGE:
- Formaldehyde:
- NOxy:
- ORAC:
- PAN:
- PERCA:
- Peroxide:
- PTRMS:
- TDLAS (1C):
- WAS Bags:
- WAS Bottles:
- Misc Non-Core**
- CASI/ATM:
- LIDAR:
- LTI:
- SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B324

Date: 03/09/2007

Instruments

1. TWC – status light came on early in the flight- too cold status light off at FL100
2. PCASP voltage dropped out due to cold soak
3. SWS some problems software prob, solved by rebooting labview

Aircraft

nil

Satcom-H Calls

Nil

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B324:

Log	Reason
Pre-flight log	No log available
Cloud Physics Processing	Processing yet to be completed.
Core Chemistry	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	4 Jan 2008	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

4 x Upward Facing Cameras
1 x Down/Rearward Facing Cameras
3 x Rearward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

Dr Clare Lee

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Met Office
Cordouan 2
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Devon
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B324 Images Emailed In Flight

B324 Sat IR 1130Z.jpg

B324 Sat Vis 1130Z.jpg

B324 EIEA51_200709031315.jpg

B324 EVUK71_200709031315.jpg